

Effects of Mastery Learning and Problem Solving Teaching Methods on Attitude to Mathematics Learning among Senior Secondary School Students in Gusau, Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study examined effects of mastery learning and problem solving teaching methods on attitude to mathematics learning among Senior Secondary School Students in Gusau, Zamfara State. Quasi-experimental research design was used for the study. Four Secondary Schools were randomly selected and assigned to experimental and control groups. A total of four hundred and fifty (450) students were used for the study. Data was collected using a 25- item Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) made up of topics in probability perceived as a difficult topic. The instrument was pilot tested and Kuder Richardson formula 21 (KR21) was used to establish the reliability coefficient ($r = 0.83$). Pre-test was administered to both the experimental and control groups to ascertain if the three groups were comparable and have the same entry characteristics before the treatment. A post-test was administered to both groups after two weeks of exposing the experimental group to mastery learning and problem solving methods and the control group to traditional/ conventional (lecture) method. Attitude and anxiety of the students towards mathematics were also tested in the study with validated instruments. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results which were significant were further analyzed with Scheffe's multiple comparison test which showed a significant difference between all the pairs (MLA and PSA; MLA and control, PSA and control. But with mastery learning having the greatest mean score. Hence it was recommended as the most efficient of the teaching methods.

Keywords: Interaction Effect, Treatment, Performance Student's Achievement, Mathematics

Introduction

Mathematics teachers need to make their teaching student-centered, give students classroom assignments and continuous assessments regularly to evaluate their performances. In order to accurately evaluate learning, an assessment method must be examined collectively (Guba & Lincoln, 1999). Assessment therefore, is an integral part of learning. The measure of certain dimensions of characteristics of human being is obtained through assessment instruments such as educational psychological tests and inventories. Unfortunately, teachers have been focusing on the cognitive domain, thereby neglecting the other aspects of assessment- affective and psycho-

motor. Research findings have shown that students demonstrate carefree and negative attitudes to Mathematics as a subject, while majority assumed that it is difficult because it deals with figures and they are generally afraid of dealing with figure/numbers (Akinsola, 1987). Ilogu (1999) also noted that positive attitude towards science, technology and Mathematics is very necessary if the nation aims at producing able scientists and technologists for national development. The author further emphasized that it is very important that science teachers adopt valid instruments or means of assessing the attitude of their students.

Mathematics is a science of quantitative relation and spatial forms in the real world, being

inseparably connected with the needs of technology and natural sciences. Mathematics according to the Cambridge international Dictionary of English 5th edition (2004) can be defined as the study or science of the numbers, quantity and space. Gowers (2005) as in Shkredov (2005) a professor of Mathematics at the University of Cambridge (UK) and a recipient of the prestigious fields medal at the historic millennium of the clay Mathematics institute sees mathematics as a lucid, dynamics subject that is relevant to diverse applications such as computer science, finance and engineering. Brown (2007) defined Mathematics as the science of skillful operations with concepts and rules inverted just for its purpose. This purpose being the skillful operations whose emphasis is on the invention of concepts.

The poor performances may be linked to the effects of negative attitudes towards the subject and poor methods of teaching some topics that students perceived difficult. Therefore, it is sad to note the sorry state of teaching and learning of Mathematics in the state. Hence, most students dislike and fail the subject. However, concerted efforts have been made to remedy this ugly situation (Nneji, 1998; Olaoye, 2002;

Adeleke, 2007; Adedayo, 2006; Akanni, 2015) but up till now the situation has not been resolved.

Over the years, there have been consistent poor performances and high failure rates in Senior Certificate Examinations in almost all the subjects in Zamfara State. This is evident in the daily complaints from state Government, Local Government Education Authorities (LGEA), Parent Teachers Associations (PTA) Individual Parents, Teachers and Community in General of the poor performances in the SSCE. The problem is also echoed daily in the States print and electronic media houses. Many students perform poorly in this subject due to one reason or the other; thereby limiting their career to progress further in their areas of interest. This is because many institutions of higher learning as well as professional bodies insist on a minimum credit pass in Mathematics for admission or employment.

The Chief examiners report 2007-2016 analysis of SSCE results showed that averagely only a small proportion of candidates passed Mathematics at credit level throughout the examination period in Zamfara State. They also appeared consistently at the last quarter of the result table. (See table 1).

Table 1: Statistics Performance in Mathematics for WAEC/SSCE Examination Results for Zamfara State from 2007 – 2016

Year	Total no of candidate who sat for SSCE		Total no of candidates who passed with credit level (1-6)		Percentage passed		Percentage failure	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
2007	8486	2000	2402	586	28.31	29.30	71.70	70.70
2008	9100	2486	2301	543	26.28	5.96	74.71	94.03
2009	10484	3100	3542	356	33.79	3.40	66.21	96.60
2010	12655	3210	3820	604	25.36	4.77	74.64	95.22
2011	14571	3300	2182	589	14.47	4.04	85.02	95.96
2012	20047	5000	5322	489	26.54	9.78	73.45	90.22
2013	20872	4000	3218	209	15.42	5.22	84.58	94.78
2014	20188	5000	5899	704	29.22	14.08	70.78	85.92
2015	18047	4000	4693	482	26.00	12.05	73.99	87.95
2016	19165	4300	5963	598	31.12	13.90	68.88	86.09

Table 1 shows a sample of the overall performance of students in WASSCE examination nationwide in 2014 regarded as the best result for the past ten years in Nigeria. Zamfara State recorded an average performance of 6.66% in Mathematics and English Language. This is indeed worrisome and urgent intervention is needed to remedy this situation. Among the reasons identified by the Chief examiners 2007-2016 for the poor performance are:

1. Failure to apply correctly source Mathematical principles

2. Inability to work to the required degree of accuracy
3. Lack of basic manipulative skills
4. Inability to visualize the component part of 3 – dimensional objects
5. Lack of required skills in geometrical construction among others.

There are two broad theoretical considerations relevant to this study. They are:

1. Polya's Theories of Teaching Mathematics.
2. Mathematics Learning Theory.

Polya (1957) theory stated that an instructor/teacher need to understand a problem, devise a plan for solving the problem, carryout the plan successfully and look back to find out that the problem has been resolved (Polya, 2014). He identified these as the four phases required in solving Mathematics problems. Polya identified problem solving as a major problem in the teaching/learning of mathematics. A problem is a difficult issue or event, which has to be solved. It is an issue which is completely new to an individual and to which he/she has no ready-made response or method of solution. Solving a problem therefore means findings a way out of a difficult situation that is unique to the problem solved:

1. Incomplete understanding of the problem owing to lack of concentration;
2. Rushing into calculations without any plans or ideas;
3. In carrying out the plans the most frequent faults are impatience and failure to read through the work

The principles in Polya's phases problem solving was applied by the researcher in providing solutions in the teaching/learning of some of the perceived difficult concept in senior secondary mathematics syllabus such as Arithmetic and Geometric Progressions, Circle Geometry, Geometrical Constructions, Probability, Bearing and Distances etc.

Mathematics learning theory by Atkinson, (1972) is an attempt to describe and explain behaviour in quantitative terms. A number of psychologists have made attempts to develop such theories (e.g Restle&Greeno, 1970). Atkinson research has primarily focused on simple language in the context of computer based instruction. Atkinson &Shiffrin (1968) discussed a model of memory based upon quantitative principles. Atkinson stated that it is possible to develop an optimal instructional strategy for a given individual provided that a detailed model of the learning process is available and that optimal learning performance can be achieved by giving each individual sufficient time to learn. Mathematic teachers need to give students class work, homework/assignment. The teacher should make sure that the classwork and assignment are marked, give students appropriate corrections identify student's weaknesses and go over and re-teach the topic and re-assess the student's weaknesses and go over and re-teach the topic and re-assess the students for optimal goal. The teacher should give students enough time to master a particular topic for perfect

understanding of the students before moving to a new topic.

Various independent studies have been conducted on the Students' difficulties in Mathematics among which Fakuade (1977);Ozoro (1978); Osifeso (1984); Iroin (1979);Taiwo (1978);Alibi (1985); Akinsola (1987); Nnaji (1988);Olaoye (2002)Adeleke (2007) and Adebayo (2006) showed diverse difficulties which the students are facing in the learning of Mathematics with different shade of opinions towards averting the difficulty.

Moreover, from table 1, it is evident that Mathematics as a core subject has not been placed in the table of subject successes. There is no gain saying that students' point at Mathematics with long sticks and many more have much difficulty solving Mathematics problems (Abakporo 2005). Again, majority of the students have irrational Mathematics phobia and fear for the subject. Therefore, urgent and appropriate remediation is needed to reduce this massive failure thereby making the subject interesting to the students. This can be done by finding appropriate solution to areas or topics that students perceive difficult which the re-occurring topics in SSCE are causing massive failure in the subject. The results of the relevant intervention programmes would go further to remedy the situation.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the difference in perceived difficulty of Senior Secondary School's Mathematics concepts between experimental and the control groups.
2. To determine the difference between the experimental group and the control group in the post-test scores of Senior Secondary School students' Attitude to Mathematics.

Hypotheses

1. There will be no significant difference in perceived difficulty of Senior Secondary School's Mathematics concepts between experimental and the control groups.
2. There will be no significant difference between the experimental group and the control group in the post-test scores of students Attitude to Mathematics.

Methodology

The study adopted quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test control group design. The study was carried out in Gusau metropolis. The target population for the study is the entire senior secondary school students of Gusau. Four hundred and fifty students (450) were selected by the use of

stratified random sampling. The sample for the study also consists of 225 males and 225 females. There were three groups made up of two treatments and one control group. One group was taught with mastery learning, the other with problem solving method while the control was taught with conventional method. Data was collected using a 25-item Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). Covering the concept of probability perceived as one of the difficult topics drawn from past WAEC questions. The instrument was pilot tested and Kuder Richardson formula 21 (KR21) was used to

establish the reliability coefficient ($r = 0.83$). Pre-test was administered to both the experimental and control groups to ascertain if the two groups are comparable and have the same entry characteristics before the treatment. A post-test was administered to both groups after two weeks of exposing the experimental group to mastery learning and problem solving methods and the control group to conventional (Lecture) teaching method. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Results

Hypothesis 1

There will be no significant difference in perceived difficulty of Senior Secondary School's Mathematics concepts between experimental and the control groups.

Table 2: The Significant difference between mastery learning, problem solving groups and control groups for Mathematics Achievement Test

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	158.493	2	79.247	0.613	.774
Within groups	13557.027	447	30.329		
Total	13715.520	449			

$P < 0.05$; $df = 447$; $f_{tab} = 0.074$ and $f_{cal} = 0.613$, Not Significant

Using the ANOVA test, we can see that the calculated f (0.613) is greater than the table f which has a value of (0.074). Recalling that the decision rule is that when the calculated f is less than the tabulated f , we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis, but when the calculated f is greater than the tabulated f , we reject the null

hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This implies that from the analysis above, we accept the null hypothesis which means that there is no significant difference in perceived difficulty of Senior Secondary School's Mathematics concepts between experimental and the control groups.

Hypothesis 2

There will be no significant difference between the experimental group and the control group in the post-test scores of students Attitude to Mathematics.

Table 3: T-test analyses of differences between the experimental group and the control group in the post-test scores of students Attitude to Mathematics

	Leven's Test for Equality of Variances		T-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	.494	.483	.340	448	.734
Equal variances not assumed			.329	273.125	.743

$P < 0.05$; $dF = 488$, $t_{tab} = 0.734$ and $t_{cal} = 0.340$, Not significant

Comparing the value of the calculated t which is 0.340 with the value from the t -table (the critical region) which is 0.734, it shows that the t -calculated is obviously less than the table value which leads us to accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis. This means that there is no significant

difference between the experimental group and the control group in the post-test scores of students Attitude to Mathematics.

Discussion of Findings

In Hypothesis 1, it was found that there was no significant difference in perceived difficulty of Senior Secondary School's Mathematics concepts between experimental and the control groups. The likely reason for this observation could be attributed to the findings of Nnaji (1988), Olaoye (2002) and Adeleke (2004) on their different studies on students' difficulties in Mathematics which showed that the students' faced the same level of difficulty in the learning of difficult concepts in mathematics. The present study is in agreement with this study with evidence which shows no significant differences in the students' level of perceived difficult concept in mathematics between the experimental and control groups at pre-test.

The second hypothesis was meant to find out if a significant difference exists between the experimental and the control groups in the post-test scores of students' attitude to mathematics. The hypothesis was accepted. The result on Table 3 shows that a non-significant t-cal of 0.494 was obtained based on the comparison of the experimental and control groups on their post-test scores on attitude. The findings of this study is connected with the conditions relating to attitude change according to Hallorah (1990) who opined that acceptance of new attitude depends on who is presenting the knowledge, how it is presented, how the person perceived it, the credibility of the communication, and the conditions by which the knowledge was received. This showed that the attitude of the students to mathematics remains same even after they have received the treatment.

Conclusion

The study examines the interaction effect between treatment (teaching methods) and performance of students' achievement in mathematics among senior secondary school students in Gusau Zamfara state, Nigeria. In the process of using the quasi experimental research pre-test post-test design, the researchers equally investigated the effects of attitude on mathematics achievement among the participants, including interaction effects of treatment and performance. It was discovered that there is no significant difference between the experimental groups and the control groups in the Post-test scores of students' attitude to mathematics. However, it was discovered that the treatment given to the groups were efficacious thus the researchers recorded significant improvement in mathematics performance among the treatment groups. This result therefore indicates that mastery learning and problem-solving methods of teaching should be adopted as teaching and learning

strategies in the classroom, to enable students to overcome their anxiety and to encourage positive attitude towards mathematics to enhance better academic achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Classroom teachers should adopt mastery learning and problem-solving techniques in the teaching and learning of difficult concepts in mathematics.
2. Teachers should be positive and supportive and should also employ teaching methods that empower students to develop healthy attitudes towards mathematics.

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